

UNDERSTANDING BOS IN A-I KNOWLEDGE VALORIZATION

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Abstract

This study aims to explore the application of Blue Ocean Strategy (BOS) principles to enhance knowledge valorization processes in Academia-Industry Collaboration (AIC) within the European Research Area. AIC involves joint efforts between academic institutions and industry entities to foster innovation, technological advancement, and economic productivity. This collaboration grants industries access to cutting-edge research, infrastructure, and skilled resources, while enabling universities to apply their research in real-world contexts.

By framing the market as a "blue ocean" of untapped opportunities rather than a "red ocean" of saturated competition, the BEAGLE project under Horizon WIDERA seeks to redefine knowledge valorization. BEAGLE leverages BOS to explore new market niches, fostering cross-sector collaboration and innovation. The findings, based on desk research and survey data, provide actionable frameworks for enhancing academia-industry partnerships and advancing AI valorization in sectors like Technology, Healthcare, and Sustainability.

Keywords: Blue Ocean Strategy, Academia-Industry Collaboration, Knowledge Valorization.

1 INTRODUCTION

Universities play a critical role in the advancement of knowledge through research, acting as custodians of intellectual heritage, disseminating insights through education, and training the next generation of researchers. These functions, while indispensable for societal and economic progress, do not always translate directly into industrial applications or immediate economic gains. The unique capacity of academic institutions to undertake research outside the scope of corporate interests ensures the provision of skills and innovations vital to a developed society [1].

However, the collaboration between academia and industry has emerged as a crucial mechanism for bridging this gap, enabling the transfer and co-creation of knowledge that drives technological advancements, innovation, and productivity. Known as Academia-Industry Collaboration (AIC), these partnerships align academic expertise with industrial needs, fostering the mutual exchange of resources and insights to create tangible value. Despite their potential, studies indicate that only 40% of such collaborations yield significant impacts on competitiveness or productivity [2]. This highlights the need for structured frameworks that enhance the effectiveness of AIC.

Knowledge valorization, the process of transforming academic insights into societal and economic benefits, is central to maximizing the potential of AIC. By emphasizing not only the generation of knowledge but also its application in real-world contexts, knowledge valorization bridges the gap between research and industry. This approach is essential for fostering innovation ecosystems that address societal challenges while creating new opportunities for economic growth.

The Blue Ocean Strategy (BOS) offers a transformative approach to knowledge valorization by encouraging the exploration of untapped markets and the creation of innovative value propositions. Unlike traditional "red ocean" strategies, which focus on competition within existing markets, BOS emphasizes the identification of "blue oceans"—uncontested market spaces with significant growth potential. This strategic framework is particularly relevant in addressing the challenges of AIC, as it provides a roadmap for creating sustainable value through interdisciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration.

Literature Review

Academia-industry collaboration has been the subject of extensive research, highlighting its potential benefits and associated challenges. Fontana [3] emphasizes the role of collaborative research in driving innovation, noting that partnerships with universities enable industries to access advanced technologies and specialized expertise. Abramo [4] underlines the importance of bibliometric analyses in measuring the impact of such collaborations, particularly in terms of patents and publications.

Beise and Stahl [5] identify academia as a critical source of external knowledge, facilitating innovation by providing new ideas and accelerating the completion of industrial projects. Similarly, Cohen [6] emphasizes the role of universities as channels for knowledge exchange, fostering an environment where theoretical insights are translated into practical applications.

Recent studies further expand on these findings. Perkmann [7] explores the dynamics of long-term partnerships between academia and industry, emphasizing the role of trust and shared goals in achieving impactful outcomes. Ranga and Etzkowitz [8] highlight the "Triple Helix" model, which integrates academia, industry, and government to foster an innovation-driven economy. Additionally, Muscio and Pozzali [9] investigate the role of intermediaries in facilitating knowledge transfer, identifying best practices for improving collaboration efficiency.

Despite these benefits, Pertuzé [2] highlights that a significant proportion of academia-industry projects fail to achieve their desired impact, often due to misaligned objectives or insufficient implementation strategies. These findings underscore the need for structured frameworks and strategies, such as BOS, to enhance the effectiveness of knowledge valorization.

The application of BOS in academia-industry collaboration is relatively novel, yet promising. By focusing on the creation of uncontested markets, BOS aligns with the objectives of knowledge valorization, enabling stakeholders to identify new opportunities and develop disruptive innovations. This approach not only enhances the competitiveness of industries but also ensures the broader societal impact of academic research.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Desk research and data collection

The desk research was conducted collaboratively by project partners using publicly available information from online repositories, published reports, and journals hosted in recognized platforms such as Web of Science (WoS). In addition to these resources, qualitative insights were gathered through interviews with stakeholders to ensure comprehensive data collection.

Data were systematically gathered using an online survey created on the EU Survey platform and accessible via the following link: https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/BEAGLE_best_practices_KV.

Partners were tasked with completing the survey based on identified best practice cases and disseminating the survey among relevant contacts to allow them to contribute directly.

The survey was structured into the following sections:

- Introductory information: Included multiple-choice questions to profile practices adopting BOS.
- Contact information: Collected details about the respondent.
- General data:
 - Name and website of the initiative.
 - Optional branding (e.g., logo).
 - Organizing institution and country.
 - Contact person.
 - Target audience (University, Industry, or Other).
 - Sectors exploring new market niches.
 - Mechanisms or formulas facilitating knowledge valorization.
 - Perceptions of achievements and optional free-text insights.

To ensure data privacy and authenticity, a consent checkbox was included for participation in BEAGLE communication activities. A privacy policy agreement managed by CTAG was also required, and there was a CAPTCHA validation to prevent automated entries.

2.2 Empirical Findings

Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive analysis was employed to summarize and interpret the collected data, serving as a foundation for more in-depth analysis. By employing methods suitable for categorical data, the analysis focused on identifying frequencies, distributions, and patterns observed in dataset [10],[11].

Key aspects of the analysis included:

- **Geographical Distribution:** Highlighted the countries implementing collaborative practices.
- **Sectoral Focus:** Examined the industry sectors targeted by these initiatives.
- **Audience and Entities:** Analyzed the composition of participants.
- **Mechanisms of Knowledge Valorization:** Reviewed the tools and strategies employed in the initiatives.

In particular, the analysis focused on best practices that adopted BOS principles. The sectors analyzed included:

- Technology and Innovation: Artificial intelligence, blockchain, IoT, renewable energy, advanced materials.
- Healthcare and Life Sciences: Personalized medicine, digital health innovations.
- Sustainability: Renewable energy, waste management, circular economy initiatives.
- Consumer Goods and Retail: Product differentiation and disruptive business models.
- Transportation and Mobility: Electric and autonomous vehicles, urban mobility solutions.
- Education and Lifelong Learning: Innovative learning platforms and professional development.
- Banking Sector: Innovative approaches in financial services.
- Other: Open-ended responses.

Mechanisms of knowledge valorization were categorized as:

- Collaborative research (e.g., public-private partnerships).
- Contract research tailored to industry needs.
- Academic consultancy and advisory services.
- Intellectual property transactions (licensing, IP sales).
- Research mobility (temporary assignments between academia and industry).
- Academic spin-offs for commercializing research.
- Labour mobility (graduate employment in industry).
- Dissemination through publications and media.
- Networking at conferences and science parks.
- Facility sharing between academia and industry.
- University-provided training for enterprises and vice versa.
- Other innovative methods as described by respondents.

Content Analysis

Content analysis provides an in-depth interpretation of survey results by systematically categorizing textual responses from open-ended questions. This research method enables researchers to code qualitative data into meaningful categories, facilitating further quantitative statistical analysis [12],[13] defines content analysis as "a research technique for the objective, systematic, and quantitative description of the manifest content of communication."

The key advantage of content analysis lies in its ability to descriptively examine communication messages, focusing on the content and the message creator. As a research tool, it is valued for its efficiency in data collection, the quality of its analysis, and its relative simplicity and safety as a methodology [14].

To ensure the robustness and validity of findings, content analysis must meet three essential criteria:

- **Objectivity:** The method must be impartial and free from researcher bias. This ensures that conclusions drawn are credible and reproducible.

- **Systematic Approach:** A structured framework is required to consistently identify and interpret content, ensuring transparency in what is included or excluded in the analysis.
- **Generality:** The results must have theoretical relevance, allowing the findings to contribute to broader academic or practical applications [15].

In this study, content analysis focuses on identifying best practices for knowledge valorization (KV) that foster collaboration between academia and industry. The methodology highlights key terms related to outcomes and learning achievements, analyzing their frequency and relevance. Additionally, it explores the relationship between the approaches adopted by best practice initiatives and their integration of Blue BOS principles.

The analysis includes profiling knowledge valorization practices that adopt BOS. This entails examining how these practices address challenges, create new opportunities, and redefine collaboration models. Through this lens, the research uncovers patterns and insights that support the development of innovative, high-impact academia-industry partnerships.

3 RESULTS

From the 113 identified initiatives and practices, a review process identified and removed 5 duplicates, reducing the dataset to 108 practices (88 external and 20 internal). Subsequently, a screening process excluded 23 additional records based on the following criteria:

- Lack of Academia-Industry Collaboration (9 records).
- Missing or incomplete information (1 record).
- Records representing projects or companies rather than best practices (13 records).

This left a final dataset of 85 unique practices and initiatives for analysis. For the purpose of this study, the distinction between internal and external origins of practices was deemed irrelevant; therefore, all data were aggregated to ensure a cohesive analysis.

The following flow diagram illustrates the process of refining and finalizing the dataset for analysis.

Figure 1 Analysis flow diagram. Own elaboration.

3.1 Descriptive analysis

This section focuses on analyzing practices that foster collaboration between academia and industry. The geographical distribution of these initiatives indicates they are implemented in almost all European Union countries, with fewer examples in Slovakia, Estonia, Latvia, Luxembourg, Malta, and the Netherlands. Additionally, practices are observed in Switzerland, the United Kingdom, and Turkey.

Spain demonstrates the highest number of initiatives, followed by France, Poland, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom. This distribution may be influenced by the project's methodology, as partners have greater knowledge and access to data from their respective countries.

From the 85 analyzed surveys, 241 sectors of focus were identified. The Technology and Innovation sector dominates (84 responses), as shown in Fig. 2. Healthcare & Life Sciences and Sustainability &

Environmental Solutions also feature prominently, representing over 10% of the total. Conversely, sectors such as Consumer Goods & Retail, Transportation & Mobility, and Education appear less frequently, reflecting their more mature markets.

Figure 2. Sectors or markets targeted by practices. Own elaboration.

The target audience for most practices (74%) includes both academia and industry. A smaller percentage (16%) exclusively targets industrial players, while 5% focus solely on academic entities. From the 85 surveys, 186 mechanisms for knowledge valorization were identified. Collaborative research emerged as the most common (47 responses), followed by academic spin-offs (32 responses), as illustrated in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Mechanism or formulas for knowledge valorization. Own elaboration.

The governance model of the initiatives reveals that approximately half (53%) are implemented by a single entity, while the remaining practices are executed by consortia comprising public universities, schools, or public administration entities.

A primary aim of identifying best practices was to evaluate whether the initiatives align with BOS principles. To achieve this, five key factors were established to assess BOS adoption:

- **Exploring New Market Niches:** The initiative generates outcomes that delve into previously untapped or underserved markets.
- **Technology Transfer to New Sectors:** The initiative facilitates the transfer of technology or knowledge into a sector that has not traditionally utilized it.
- **Unique Provider Status:** The initiative creates results that establish the organization as the sole provider of a product, service, or innovation, eliminating direct competition.
- **Sector-Specific Exclusivity:** The outcomes of the initiative are the only solutions available within a specific sector.
- **Disruptive Value Proposition:** The initiative delivers a novel or disruptive value proposition, addressing customer needs previously unmet by traditional offerings.

The analysis depicted in Fig. 4, indicates that Factor 2 (technology transfer to new sectors) and Factor 5 (disruptive value propositions) are the most frequently observed, with 30 and 29 instances, respectively. Factor 1 (exploring new market niches) follows closely, appearing 25 times. In contrast, Factor 4 (sector-

specific exclusivity) and Factor 3 (unique provider status) were less common, with frequencies of 9 and 8, respectively.

Additionally, the “Other” category, which represents non-conclusive instances of BOS adoption, was noted 29 times, highlighting areas where further refinement or clarity may be needed in applying BOS principles.

Figure 4. Analysis of factors addressing BOS. Own elaboration.

3.2 Content analysis

This section presents a detailed content analysis of best practices that facilitate collaboration between academia and industry, with particular attention to practices incorporating the Blue Ocean Strategy (BOS).

A total of 85 best practices were identified at the conclusion of the screening process. Each practice was analyzed to evaluate its outcomes and the lessons learned. The Fig. 5a illustrates a word cloud highlighting the most frequently mentioned terms across these practices. Words such as *research*, *project* and *innovation* emerge prominently, reflecting the primary focus areas of these initiatives.

Focusing specifically on initiatives adopting BOS, Fig. 5b presents a word cloud of key terms associated with their outcomes and learning. Similar terms surface, but with a stronger emphasis on *research*, *development*, *project*, *digital*, *market*, *company*, *working*, *new*, *energy*, and *technology*. These terms underscore the strategic focus of BOS-driven initiatives.

Figure 5. a) Key themes within the best practices. b).key themes within the best practices initiatives that adopt BOS. Both wordcloud descriptions of key themes are own elaboration.

The ideal profile for knowledge valorization through BOS is defined by five factors determined by the research team (as outlined previously). Fig. 6 compares the aggregated profile of identified practices with this ideal BOS profile, illustrating how closely current practices align with the theoretical benchmark.

Fig. 6 presents a flow diagram analyzing the relationship between different types of initiatives and their adoption of BOS. On the left-hand side, the diagram shows the initiatives and their proportional representation. The right-hand side indicates the extent to which each initiative type adopts BOS.

Key observations include:

- Common initiatives, such as *transferring technology to a new sector* and *offering a disruptive new value proposition* targeting underserved customer segments, show moderate adoption of BOS, with rates of 25% and 32%, respectively.

- Initiatives targeting *new market niches* demonstrate higher BOS adoption, with 40% employing the strategy.
- Less common but highly BOS-aligned initiatives include those aiming to become the sole provider in a specific sector (50% BOS adoption) or deliver unique outcomes with no competitors (44% BOS adoption).

Figure 6. Analysis of the profile of practice on knowledge valorisation adopting BOS. Own elaboration.

Fig. 7 illustrates a flow diagram analyzing the relationship between the strategic approach of each best practice initiative and its adoption of the Blue Ocean Strategy (BOS). On the left side, the diagram displays the various initiatives along with the percentage they represent within the total sample. On the right side, it shows the proportion of each initiative type that has adopted BOS.

Figure 7. Flow diagram of best practices initiatives and the adoption or not of BOS. Own elaboration.

Among the most common initiatives, three stand out:

- **Transferring technology to a new sector.**
- **Generating results that penetrate deeply into new market niches.**
- **Offering a disruptive value proposition that targets previously underserved or unaddressed customers.**

Despite their prominence, the adoption of BOS within these initiatives remains moderate:

- Initiatives focused on *transferring technology to a new sector* adopt BOS in only 25% of cases.
- Initiatives offering a *disruptive new value proposition* targeting underserved customers show a 32% adoption rate.

- Initiatives penetrating *new market niches* demonstrate a higher adoption rate, with **40%** employing BOS principles.

Less common initiatives show a stronger alignment with BOS:

- Initiatives aimed at becoming a **sole provider in their sector**, where the results create a unique and uncontested offering, have a **50%** BOS adoption rate.
- Initiatives producing outcomes that are **the only available solution within a sector** adopt BOS in **44%** of cases.

Fig. 7 visually represents these dynamics, highlighting the relationship between initiative types and the adoption of BOS. The findings suggest that while BOS adoption varies across initiatives, it is particularly well-suited to approaches emphasizing exclusivity and innovation in untapped market spaces.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This research underscores the critical role of knowledge valorization and co-creation in fostering effective collaborations between academia and industry. By addressing the mechanisms, challenges, and impacts of these processes, we can drive innovation, promote economic growth, and advance societal development. Building strong networks and adaptable communities is essential for maximizing the benefits of academic research and facilitating meaningful collaborations.

To assess the capacity or opportunity for adopting the BOS, this study explored a range of approaches. The findings reveal that only initiatives targeting results in untapped market niches, exploring uncontested spaces, or establishing a unique position within their sector align closely with BOS principles. This suggests that most practices remain entrenched in the "red ocean" of competition, presenting an opportunity for Knowledge Transfer Offices (KTOs), Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs), and corporate innovation units to design and implement knowledge valorization practices that embrace BOS principles.

Consistent with the literature review, collaborations between academia and industry grant companies access to expertise and capabilities that enhance products, processes, and overall innovation. Notably, the Technology and Innovation sector, Healthcare and Life Sciences, and Sustainability and Environmental Solutions account for more than 60% of the identified practices, reflecting their dominance in fostering collaborative initiatives. Conversely, sectors such as finance and entertainment exhibit lower levels of collaboration, highlighting untapped potential for expanding industry-academia engagement in these areas.

The analysis indicates that 74% of the initiatives aim to strengthen collaboration between academia and industry, underscoring the importance of mutual engagement. In contrast, 16% of initiatives are industry-specific, addressing targeted industrial needs, while only 5% focus exclusively on academia, reflecting the relative rarity of intra-academic knowledge transfer. This preference for mutual collaboration reinforces the value of strategies that connect academia and industry rather than isolating them.

Fig. 3 illustrates the diverse strategies employed to facilitate knowledge transfer between academia and industry. Collaborative research emerges as the most common approach, adopted by 47 initiatives. This strategy fosters joint efforts between researchers and industry professionals, enabling the exchange of expertise and resources. Academic spin-offs, the second most prevalent strategy (32 initiatives), focus on commercializing academic research through new companies, often startups, translating innovations into marketable products and services. These findings highlight the importance of collaborative and entrepreneurial approaches in bridging the gap between theoretical research and practical applications.

The findings offer valuable insights into the diverging choices of knowledge valorization strategies. Collaborative research and academic spin-offs are strongly associated with the most represented sectors—Technology and Innovation, Healthcare and Life Sciences, and Sustainability and Environmental Solutions. However, a significant challenge lies in clearly defining concepts, particularly BOS, and effectively communicating them to stakeholders.

The predominance of red ocean strategies among best practices can be attributed to the ease of defining and delimiting criteria for participation. However, a lack of awareness and understanding of BOS principles presents a critical gap. While initiatives may pursue approaches that align with BOS, such as targeting new

market niches or developing innovative business models, these efforts often lack intentionality or recognition.

The BEAGLE project makes significant strides in applying BOS to knowledge valorization, providing a model for other initiatives to emulate. Its approach demonstrates how BOS can maximize the impact of innovation and foster market creation. The lack of focus on new market niches in existing best practices highlights the need for greater awareness of BOS and its potential benefits. Moving forward, efforts should prioritize communicating the advantages of BOS and encouraging its adoption in knowledge valorization initiatives.

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